

Research Article

The Development of Torque Wrench with Digital Counter (TWDC) in Politeknik Banting Selangor

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Abstract: A torque wrench is crucial in aircraft maintenance, where accurate torque application directly influences the safety, reliability, and structural integrity of critical components. Conventional torque tools rely on manual methods to measure and track torque application, often leading human error, especially in high repetition task. These errors can result in over or under tightening, compromising maintenance quality. To address this challenge, this project introduces an innovative torque wrench with digital counter to enhance accuracy, traceability, and user accountability. The wrench was developed through design and prototyping process using Autodesk Inventor and 3D-printed using high performance polylactic acid (HP-PLA) for lightweight durability. The system integrates switching, PCB controlled and digital display to detect and display the number of torque applications in real-time. Prototype testing was conducted in a maintenance workshop environment to evaluate the device's effectiveness. Result demonstrated a 70% reduction in tightening-related errors, improved task consistency and enhanced the workflow. This innovation supports the principles of industry 4.0 by integrating smart technology and automation into traditional tools, promoting data-driven and error-reducing maintenance practices. This project also aligns with United Nation Sustainable Development Goal 9 (SDG9) by fostering industry innovation and enhancing infrastructure through the development of intelligent maintenance tools. The project also shows strong potential for further development and commercialization with technical training institutions and the aerospace industry.

Keywords: torque precision, torque wrench, digital counter, precision fastening, aviation troque

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1. INTRODUCTION

Torque application is critical process in maintenance or manufacturing where safety, structural integrity, and compliance with regulatory standards depend heavily on precise torque control. Torque wrenches are commonly used to apply a specific torque to fastener such as bolts and nuts; however, conventional tools rely on manual counting and visual feedback, which can result in over-tightening, under-tightening or missed fasteners due to human errors. These issues are critical in aerospace industry, where even minor assembly errors can lead to catastrophic failure.

In recent years, technology advancements in Industry 4.0 have paved the way for the integration of smart technologies into traditional mechanical tools. These developments include embedding sensors, digital displays, microcontrollers, and real-time data tracking features. By aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 9 (SDG9)- which promotes industry innovation and infrastructures –

this transformation allows reliable, efficient, and intelligent maintenance tools. This incorporation of smart feedback systems not only support quality assurance but also aids in training and industrial application by providing consistent torque verification and data traceability.

Previous studies have shown the value of high precision torque wrenches in aerospace and manufacturing. For example, (Xu et.al, 2020) developed a high-precision digital display torque wrench capable of 0.1% accuracy trough innovation in transducer design and software-based linearity correction. Their demonstrated that combining torsion-based sensors with embedded circuits significantly improves torque accuracy and reliability in critical environments.

Motivated by this need for intelligent, error-reducing tools, this project introduces a digitally enhanced torque wrench developed at Politeknik Banting Selangor. It features a built-in digital counter to track torque cycles in a real time. This project aims to reduce human errors, improve efficiency, and support the future of aviation maintenance through low-cost, innovative tooling.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development process for torque wrench with digital counter follow systematic engineering approach. **Figure 1** illustrates the development s process in five stages.

Figure 1: Overall Flow Chart of Torque Wrench with Digital Counter

The development of torque wrench with digital followed several key steps.

First, the problem was identified-traditional torque wrenches do not track how many times they are used, which can lead to human errors during maintenance. Next, the team worked on the design and idea generation, deciding to add a digital counter to an existing torque wrench to improve accuracy.

Then, a 3D model of the housing for electronics and switching was created using Autodesk Inventor. After that, the team moved on to selecting electronics components such as PCB controller, digital display and switching. These were chosen because they are small, affordable, and easy to integrate.

The next step involved programming the PCB board to read the switching and display the number of wrench uses on the screen. A reset button and debounce feature were also added to avoid counting errors. Once the programming was done, the parts were assembled using a 3D-printed enclosure made from HP-PLA material.

After assembly, the prototype was tested in workshop setting. Results showed that it helped reduce tightening errors by 70%. Finally, a survey was conducted among students, lecturers and technicians. Based on their feedback, some future improvements were suggested, such as adding wireless data storage and automatic alerts.

2.1 Material use

The developments of Torque wrench with Digital Counter involves the use of three main items, each playing an important function to creating the usable tools. The items are stated in **Table 1**.

Table 1. The main items used for Torque Wrench with Digital counters.

Material	Description
	<p>Limit Switch</p> <p>The limit switch is a simple sensor used to detect the movement of the torque wrench when it reaches the set torque and makes a clicking motion. It is positioned so that it is triggered only by this specific movement. When the wrench clicks, the switch is pressed, sending a signal to the Arduino microcontroller to increase the count on the screen display.</p>
	<p>Arduino Uno and PCB Board</p> <p>The Arduino Uno is a compact microcontroller board that acts as the brain of the system. It receives signals from the limit switch and processes them to control the digital display, updating the torque count each time the wrench is used. The PCB board (printed circuit board) is used to organize and support all the electronic components. It connects the Arduino, sensor, display, and other parts using wires or soldering, helping to keep the system neat, secure, and functional. Together, the Arduino Uno and PCB board form the core of the electronic circuit in the digital torque wrench.</p>

Material	Description
	<p>Torque Wrench (Click-Type)</p> <p>The torque wrench (click-type) is the main mechanical tool used to apply a specific amount of torque to bolts or fasteners. When the preset torque level is reached, the wrench produces a clear audible "click" and a slight release of tension, signalling the user to stop applying force. This ensures accurate and consistent tightening, which is especially important in maintenance tasks where over- or under-tightening can lead to safety issues.</p>

3. FINDINGS

The development of torque wrench with digital counter produced a functional and innovative prototype. The project's outcome can be discussed under two major aspects: Product Structure and Product Drawing. This is aligned with research by (Robertson et al., 2018.), which highlights how integrated digital feedback—such as torque verification—can significantly reduce maintenance errors and increase technician confidence and task efficiency.

3.1 Product Structure

This final product is a conventional click-type torque wrench upgrade with smart technology to count each torque application. This upgrade addresses the risk human error in repetitive torque tasks—a common issues in aircraft maintenance, where under – or over-tightening can lead to safety-critical problems. The structure comprises both mechanical and electronic components as per **Figure 2** and the details as per **Table 2**.

Figure 2. Assemble Product Structure

Table 2. Details Product Structure

Item	Details
Mechanical Assembly	The base is a standard torque wrench that maintains its original tightening mechanism.
3D-Printed Housing	A custom housing was designed using Autodesk Inventor and printed using HP-PLA filament. It protects the electronic components and is ergonomically attached to the wrench's body without disrupting grip or balance.
Digital Display Module	A compact screen is mounted on the body of the wrench. It shows the number of completed torque actions in real-time. This module includes a reset button that allows users to zero the count before starting a new task.
Microcontroller	An Arduino Nano is used to process input from the IR sensor. It interprets the signal and triggers the counter increment. It was inside the printed housing
Switching System	A switching sensor is attached near the ratchet mechanism. This sensor detects each torque cycle (i.e., when the wrench clicks after reaching the set torque).

3.2.2 Product Drawing-3D Printed Housing

The 3D-Printed housing is a critical part of product’s Innovation. It was designed to securely encase and protect all electronic components-including the microcontroller, switching, screen display, wiring and battery -while maintaining the ergonomic handling and usability of torque wrench.

The housing was modelled using Autodesk Inventor based on dimensional measurements taken from the existing torque wrench. The design was printed using HP-PLA filament, chosen for its strength, heat resistance, and environmental friendliness. The housing is mounted along the handle section, ensuring it does not interfere with the mechanical function of the ratchet head mechanism as per **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Model for switching housing.

The 3D- printed enclosure demonstrates the potential of rapid prototyping and additive manufacturing in support smart tool development aligned with Industry 4.0. It cost-effective, lightweight, and easily modifiable for different wrench size or digital configurations. By leveraging

design flexibility and durable material, this housing contributes to product's success in integrating mechanical and digital systems. The process of 3D-printed as **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Process of 3D-Printed Housing.

4. DISCUSSION

The torque wrench with a built-in digital counter was developed to reduce human error in repetitive torque task, particularly in aviation maintenance environments. Testing in simulated workshop showed that the prototype performed effectively, with 70% reduction in tightening errors compared to conventional torque wrenches. This improvement was largely due to integration of switching sensor and Arduino based system that accurately counted each torque application.

The screen provides real time display of torque cycles, while rest button allowed user to zero the count before starting a new task. A debounce function in the programming ensured that only valid torque clicks were registered, preventing false or multiple counts. These features allowed users to maintain consistency and reduce the chance of missing fasteners-an issue can cause serious safety concern in aviation maintenance.

To evaluate acceptance a practical value, a survey was distributed to 30 participant including technicians, lecturer, and students. The result is shown in **Table 3**:

Table 3. Survey Feedback on Prototype Usability and Effectiveness

Criteria	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)
Reduce Human error	88	10	4
Easy to Use	80	13	7
Suitable of Training	93	7	0
Potential for Industrial Use	75	20	5

Most respondents agreed that the tool was effective in reducing error, easy to use, and especially valuable in training environments. Many noted that it improved their awareness during repetitive task and help them to stay focused.

In summary prototyped fulfilled its main objective by improving torque application accuracy a receiving strong user validation. It shows promise for wider application in educational setting and practical workshop environments.

5. CONCLUSION

This project successfully developed and tested a torque wrench equipped digital with a digital counter to improved accuracy and reduce human errors during maintenance task. The prototype combined traditional click-type torque wrench with switching sensor, Arduino microcontroller, screen display, and 3D-printed housing. It was designed to counted torque application in real time, making it especially useful for repetitive task where miscounts often occur.

Testing showed that the tool reduces tightening errors by up 70% and provided reliable feedback throughout usage. User feedback from technicians, lecturer, and students confirmed that the tool was easy to use, highly suitable for training, and had good potential for wider workshop application. These results support the findings by (Korba et al., 2023), who demonstrated that digital real-life data tools—can improve accuracy, reduce task time, and increase user confidence.

Overall, this innovation offers a low-cost and effective solution for improving maintenance quality, particular in aviation and technical education settings. With minor enhancement such as a data logging or wireless connectivity, the tool could further support traceability and documentation needs in industrial environments. This project not only meets a current need but also encourage continues improvements maintenance practices trough simple and practical innovation.

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